
Pest management and control

DISEASES

The appearance of tungro symptoms in boro paddy in W. Bengal, India

S. Mukhopadhyay, A.B. Ghosh, P. Tarafder, and Miss S. Chakvarty
Department of Plant Pathology (Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya), Kalyani, Nadia, W. Bengal, India

Serious epidemics of tungro occurred in W. Bengal in 1969 and the disease has occurred sporadically since then. To combat its spread in India, extensive research has been conducted at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at Hyderabad, the Central Rice Research Institute at Cuttack, the Indian Agricultural Research Institute at New Delhi, and at Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya (department of plant pathology) in W. Bengal. As a result, adequate cultivation practices were recommended such as removal of the virus sources from fields, growing tolerant or resistant varieties, and judicious pesticide application to control the vector.

Although no serious incidence of tungro has been reported in W. Bengal during the last 3 years, its presence is evident from symptoms in trial plots at the Chinsurah Rice Research Station and at the plant virus experimental fields at Kalyani. Because epidemics of tungro could spread under favorable conditions, rice fields around Kalyani were searched for tungro during the boro season, 1976–77 (the disease was found in a more or less epidemic form in one field).

In the field study at Kalyani, tungro-like symptoms were found in the first week of February 1977 on a few plants of the variety China (imported from Bangladesh) grown in lowland conditions. The leaves turned orange-yellow and the plants became stunted. The height of infected plants was reduced by 15 to 96%.

In transmission studies with TN1 seedlings, typical symptoms developed within 20 days of inoculation. The

sweeping technique yielded no leafhoppers. Patches of diseased plants gradually appeared and the disease spread during March. At the end of March, the leafhopper population, primarily *Nephotettix virescens*, was high (12 adults/sweep). During early April, the entire field was diseased, and the leafhopper population remained high. The crop – harvested on 8 April – yielded a low 1.27 t/ha (the expected yield was 5.56 t/ha).

In the adjacent highland situation, Ratna was transplanted in the second week of February. The field remained normal and yields were optimum. Neither the sweeping technique nor the light trap yielded leafhoppers. The macroclimatic situation at Kalyani and that in the field being studied are similar because the two locations are no more than 1 km apart. But the microclimatic situation may differ, resulting in a buildup of hoppers at Kalyani.

In a study of the biology of *Nephotettix virescens*, 33.3% hatching was observed during December-January 1976. It took from 28 to 43 days for molting to be completed (1st-5th instar) and for adults to emerge. From 5 to 19% of the adults appeared. ❧

Alternate hosts of rice tungro virus and its vectors

Central Rice Research Institute,
G. Mohana Rao and A. Anjaneyuzul
Cuttack-753006, Orissa, India.

Information on the survival of tungro virus and its vectors *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus* during off-seasons is vital to the understanding of its epidemiology. Seventeen wild species of rice, 20 of weeds, and 6 of cereal crops were tested to see if they might support tungro virus and its vectors during off-seasons.

The weed and cereal crop species showed no visible symptoms of tungro, nor did they act as symptomless carriers. But the virus infected and survived on nine of the wild rices: *Oryza glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, the introgressive form of *Oryza* sp., *O. barthii*, *O. perennis*, *O. eichengeri*, *O. australiensis*, *O. punctata*, and *O. brachyantha*. However, the virus was recovered through back indexing with nonviruliferous *N. virescens* only from the first five species, even though the remaining four were clearly stunted. Some peculiar symptoms not common on rice cultivars were observed in some species, including veinal and interveinal necrosis.

In tests of vectors, plant species on which leafhoppers survived for more than 10 days were considered favorable food hosts; those that supported a complete life cycle were considered reproductive hosts. The most efficient tungro vector, *N. virescens*, had a more limited host range than the inefficient vector *N. nigropictus*.

The reproductive host species of *N. virescens* in order of decreasing favorableness were *O. sativa*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. perennis*, *Paspalum orbiculare*, and *Echinochloa colonum*. Its food hosts were the species *O. barthii*, *O. perreiri*, and *Eleusine indica*. The reproductive host species of *N. nigropictus* in order of decreasing favorableness were *Leersia hexendra*, *O. sativa*, *O. glaberrima*, *E. colonum*, *P. orbiculare*, *O. nivara*, *O. malampzhuaensis*, *O. perennis*, *O. punctata*, *O. officinalis*, *Ischaemum indicum*, *O. eichengeri*, and *O. minuta*. The food host species for this vector in order of decreasing favorableness were *O. barthii*, *Eleusine coracana*, *Hordeum vulgare*, *Triticum vulgare*, *Zea mays*, *O. perreiri*, *E. indica*, and *O. alta*. ❧

Geographic distribution of tungro virus disease and its vectors in India

A. Anjaneyulu and N. K. Chakrabarti,
Central Rice Research Institute,
Cuttack-753006, Orissa, India

Because the tungro virus syndrome is complex, diagnosis of the disease can be

Positive identification of tungro virus disease by transmission tests in different locations in India.

Year	State	District	Locations where positive results were obtained ^a	Extent of disease
1971	Andhra Pradesh	West Godavari	Maruteru	Moderate
1972	Bihar	Sasaram	Sasaram	Mild
	West Bengal	Hooghli	Chinsurah	Mild
	Orissa	Cuttack	CRR I Farm	Mild
1973	Orissa	Cuttack	CRR I Farm, Imamnagar	Mild
		Sambalpur	Chiplima	Moderate
	West Bengal	Nadia	Ranaghat, Krishnagar, Habibpur	Severe
		Burdwan	Debipur, Bhatar Farm, Sarul, Pemra	Severe
		Hooghli	Chinsurah	Severe
	Tripura	West Tripura	Jangalia, Nalchar, Seasrimai, Vishalgarh, Gokulnagar	Severe
	Assam	Nowgong	Rangbeng	Moderate
Cacher		Gusaipur	Moderate	
Manipur	Central	Samanroll, Wanghal	Mild	
1974	Kerala	Allepey	Kuttanadu area	Moderate

^aCRR I = Central Rice Research Institute.

confirmed only through transmission tests. This method showed the occurrence of tungro earlier in the Indian states of West Bengal, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, and Kerala. From 1971 to 1974, the authors collected suspected tungro samples from 30 locations in 8 Indian states and conducted transmission tests on them.

Tungro disease in general was found to be a problem in northeastern, eastern, and southern India (see table). For still unknown reasons, it occurs in epidemic form only in certain years. Epidemics

occurred in parts of northeastern and eastern India in 1969 and 1973, and in the Kuttanadu area of Kerala in 1974.

The two green leafhopper vectors of tungro, *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, are found throughout India, and high populations are recorded in the states of Assam, Manipur, Tripura, West Bengal, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh. Although tungro is generally spread by *N. virescens*, it was associated with *N. nigropictus* in Kerala in 1974 and Manipur in 1973. ❧

Incidence of sheath rot on three rice varieties

D. Koteswara Rao, Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, West Godavari, Andhra Pradesh, India

Severe incidence of sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae* was observed on three dwarf rice varieties – IR32, CR73-7, and Sona – at the Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh, during the rabi season (Dec.–Apr.) of 1972–73. Oblong, chocolate-colored spots, some with light centers,

developed on the top leaf sheaths. Most of the leaf-sheath areas were dark brown because the spots had coalesced. The panicles of some diseased tillers emerged only partially. A white fungus growth consisting of hyphae, conidia, and conidiophores was observed on the inner surfaces of the infected sheaths.

The spots were from 4 to 18 mm long and from 2 to 7 mm wide (see table). In Sona, 31% of the tillers were infected; in IR22, 9%; and in CR73-7, 10%. Disease incidence at the station was insignificant in 1974 and 1975. ❧

Size of sheath rot spots and disease incidence in three rice varieties. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Variety	Size of sheath rot spot (mm)		Diseased hills (%)	Diseased tillers (%)
	Range	Av.		
IR22	4–16 × 3–6	9.6 × 4.2	77	9
CR73-7	5–17 × 2–6	9.6 × 4.3	80	10
Sona	6–18 × 2–7	9.3 × 4.3	97	31

Chemical seed treatment to control Udbatta disease of paddy

N. Shivanandappa, Jr. pathologist, Regional Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Mission Compound, Shimoga, Karnataka, India

Udbatta caused by *Ephelis oryzae* is an increasingly important disease of paddy that causes considerable yield loss in Karnataka state. The disease affects both high yielding and local varieties. Estimated losses have been from 246.91 to 493.82 kg/ha, depending on disease incidence and intensity. The disease is reportedly borne in the seed, and symptoms show at the time of flowering.

The control measure currently recommended — keeping the seeds at 52–54°C for 20 min before sowing — is difficult for farmers to follow. Hence an experiment was conducted on chemical control. The treatments were Benlate, Bavistin, and Vitavax at 400 mg/kg of seed; hot water at 54°C for 20 minutes; and a control. Chemical-treated seeds were kept in cloth bags for 12 hours before sowing. Three-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill and observed for disease incidence at panicle initiation and grain formation stages.

Three seasons' data indicated that Benlate, Bavistin, and hot water were all superior to the control, while Benlate and Bavistin controlled the disease as well as hot water. ❧

“Rice abortion” or sheath rot—a serious rice disease in Thailand

Arunee Surin, rice pathologist; and Somkid Disthaporn, head, Rice Diseases Branch, Plant Pathology Division, Bangkok, Thailand

“Rice abortion” is the name that Thai farmers have given to a widespread disorder of rice with characteristics similar to those of sheath rot disease. It was first reported in 1969 as a secondary factor associated with stem borers, and has become increasingly serious, especially in the major rice-growing area of central Thailand. In 1975 the disease completely destroyed about 500 ha in Chachoengsao province. In severe cases, more than 70% of the infected plants produced no panicles.